

Theoretical Foundations of Organizing Students' Independent Work

Yakubova Barno Baxtiyorovna

Senior teacher of the Department of "Humanities", Andijan Institute of Machine building, City of Andijan, Uzbekistan

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Abstract: The main goal of higher education is to prepare qualified, competitive specialists capable of working effectively in the labor market. High-quality education is strongly associated with the objectives of organizing, monitoring, and evaluating students' independent work. Independent study is an integral part of the university curriculum.

Keywords: Professional education, teacher, project, development, referencing, citation, annotation, referral.

Given that different subjects have different goals and objectives, it is impossible to establish a single set of tasks for independent work (IW), but it is possible to help teachers by compiling an optimal set of IW types and forms, such as: - working with recommended and independently selected literature necessary for solving professional tasks; - preparing various types of answer plans and presentation plans on topics; - developing a summary, a summary-scheme, writing an annotation, review, or abstract for an article or book; - creating tables, clusters, and control tasks (including in test form); - participating in discussions and brainstorming; - formulating answers to problematic questions using additional literature; - resolving problem situations with oral and written argumentation; - developing a problem situation to address a specific problematic issue; - searching for knowledge to answer a problematic question; - performing research tasks in accordance with a research project; - preparing reports and other assignments.[1.2] The methods of written fixation of the studied material include: annotation, thesis writing, referencing, note-taking, quoting, and logical structuring.

Let us consider their essence. Annotation - from Latin *annotatio* - a remark, a brief description of the content of the work. The length of an annotation depends on the size of the source, but most often does not exceed 0.5-1 typed pages. Each book is usually accompanied by an annotation placed on the back of its title page. [2.60]

Thesis - from Greek *thesis* - a position or statement; in a broad sense, any assertion in a dispute or presentation of a theory. Thesis writing involves composing brief notes that reflect the main, essential connections and facts of the read text. Theses reflect the main points of the work, conclusions, and proposals. The volume of a thesis is typically 1-2 pages.

Abstract - from Latin *refero* - to report, a brief written presentation of the content of a scientific work. A student's abstract typically summarizes a number of works related to a single topic and aims to deepen the study of a particular problem. Writing an abstract presupposes the presence of the author's position on the problem under consideration. [3.4]

Concept - from Latin *conspicere* - review, brief exposition, record of the content of any composition or report. It is compiled to present and preserve the main content of what has been read. Text outline - division of text into parts according to logic and number of information units, highlighting the main ideas in each part and defining headings. [4.205]

Learning involves active participation of both teachers and students. No matter how hard the teacher tries, if students do not work, there is no learning process. The main goal is to teach students to work independently. A true teacher is not one who teaches, but one from whom students learn. Teaching involves the teacher conveying certain knowledge and managing the process of its assimilation. It is not enough to provide information; it is necessary to help develop skills of academic work and the ability to use acquired knowledge. One way to activate students' cognitive activity is to organize and conduct various independent tasks. [5.223] These occupy an exceptional place in modern lessons because students acquire knowledge only through independent activity. Students must work in class under the guidance of teachers. Passively listening and memorizing from a textbook is far from true knowledge. What is firmly and well mastered is that which is obtained through active personal effort. Independent work first compels, then teaches students to seek answers to questions, read additional literature, identify the main and essential points, explain and interpret natural phenomena, think and search, formulate hypotheses - in other words, ultimately acquire knowledge. Independent work is the most important and indispensable part of any lesson because it eliminates idle time, engages the mind, and allows for firmer and deeper assimilation of the studied material. Independent work should be diverse, with optimal duration for each class. As K.D. Ushinsky aptly said: "A child requires constant activity and tires not from activity itself, but from its uniformity and one-sidedness." Independent learning is understood as any organized student activity aimed at fulfilling a set didactic goal in a specially allocated time: finding knowledge, comprehending it, reinforcing it, forming and developing skills and abilities, generalizing and systematizing knowledge. Experts in this field emphasized that it is important to provide students with a method, a guide for organizing and acquiring knowledge, which means equipping them with skills and abilities for the scientific organization of mental work, i.e., the ability to set goals, choose means to achieve them, and plan work over time. To form a holistic and harmonious personality, it is necessary to systematically engage it in independent activity, which, through a special type of educational task - independent work - acquires the character of problem-solving and exploratory activity. The fundamental requirement of society for modern education is the formation of individuals who can independently and creatively solve scientific, industrial, and social problems, think critically, develop and defend their points of view and beliefs, systematically and continuously replenish and update their knowledge through self-education, improve their skills, and creatively apply them in practice. [6.180] To achieve these goals, we can highlight the following requirements for organizing students' independent work:

- Any independent work during a lesson should have a specific goal, and the student should understand how to achieve it.
- The independent work should align with the student's learning capabilities.
- The progression from one level of difficulty to another must be gradual.
- The teacher ensures a combination of various types of independent work and manages the work process itself.

Independent work should have minimal standardization, as its main objective is to develop the student's cognitive abilities, initiative, and creativity. Various types of independent work are employed in the learning process. They can be classified according to different criteria: didactic purpose, the nature of students' learning activities, content, degree of students'

independence, and element of creativity. [7.140] According to the didactic purpose, independent work can be divided into five groups:

- Acquisition of new knowledge, mastering the ability to acquire knowledge independently;
- consolidation and refinement of knowledge;
- development of the ability to apply knowledge in solving educational and practical tasks;
- formation of practical skills and abilities;
- cultivation of creative thinking and the ability to apply knowledge in complex situations. [8.730]

Learning assignments for independent work can, in turn, be divided:

1. By the method of students' independent work:

observation;

exercise;

work with the textbook. [9.16]

2. By stages of the educational process:

perception task;

task for systematization;

task for reinforcing the learning material;

task for reviewing the learning material.

3. By the nature of the student's cognitive activity:

reproductive tasks;

creative (productive) tasks;

4. By the nature of guidance:

detailed instructions;

less detailed instructions. [10.43]

5. By the nature of the leadership:

detailed instructions;

less detailed instructions. [11.4]

Independent learning and research work contribute to a deep understanding of the subject and foster the ability to analyze, comprehend, and evaluate contemporary events. They also enable solving professional problems by uniting theory and practice, which ensures successful mastery of the profession. [12.3]

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